

Extension of Sarbanes-Oxley Act Provisions in the Public Financial Management in Ghana

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Abstract

This study measures the relative importance of extending the Sarbanes-Oxley Act (SOX, 2002) provisions to the public financial management in Ghana. It targets at the possibility of adopting the SOX Act in the local government sector in Ghana. The survey targeted, government officials, specifically Public Sector Finance Officers and university lecturers with relevant knowledge in PFM, External Auditors and Accountants. The trend of the responses implies that apart from the introduction of an independent audit committee into the public sector; the participants mainly supports the provision of a public accounting oversight board. They recommend that the non-audit service should not pre-approved by the audit committee. We also found strong support for auditor independences rules similar to the SOX Act provisions. Whiles majority of lecturers believe that extending the SOX Act provision to Ghana's PFM is not a means to an end, they believe that the PFM ACT (2016) Act 921 have enough provisions to deal with most systemic challenges in the local government sector in Ghana

Key Words: Public Financial Management, Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002, Public Financial Management Act (2016) Act 921, Local government

1. Introduction

Corporate Governance describes 'the framework of rules, relationships, systems and processes within and by which authority is exercised and controlled in organizations. It encompasses the mechanisms by which companies, and those in control, are held to account'. Corporate governance is therefore a means by which companies and other entities for example public entities alike discharge their accountability to their stakeholders. Public accountability is an important element in PFM that cannot be downplayed; it is earned by an accountable, transparent, controllable and responding government as these elements tells how discipline and responsible a government is. Absence of accountability, there is space for fulmination and abuse of power, corruption and totalitarianism(Loozekoot & Dijkstra, 2017). For these cause, accountability is the legitimating foundation of democracy (Flinders, 2017) and must be stringently observed and applied in manner of democratic endeavours. Therefore for any developing country to achieve it desired goal of eradicating poverty and creating wealth for it populace then public accountability should never be downplayed.

The ACCA global (2013) defines Public Financial Management as a process that affects the way funding is used to address and manage national and local priorities, the availability of resources for investment and the cost-effectiveness of public services. Onuorah and Appah (2012), suggest public financial management as the planning, organizing, procurement and utilization of government financial resources as well as the formulation of appropriate policies in order to achieve the aspirations of members of a society. According to Premchand (1999) public financial management is the link between the community's aspirations with resources, and the contemporary times with future and therefore lies at the very heart of the operations and the fiscal policy of government. It can be concluded that public financial management implies all government activity that includes but not limited to the mobilisation of revenue mainly to improving and enhancing the quality of public service outcomes, decision-making and long-term sustainability of public services leading to a desirable outcome that the general public will have greater trust in the public services and the finance professional if there is strong financial stewardship, accountability and transparency in the use of public funds.

It is therefore paramount for governments to enact policies and strategies that can protect public purse to boost public confidence in the financial administration of tax payer's money. It was against this background the US congress in 2002 enacted the Sarbanes-Oxley Act (SOX) to protect shareholders and other stakeholder's interest in public companies. Whether this policy has been successful or not the researchers want to know the extent to which this enactment (SOX) can be extended to the public financial administration in Ghana. According to Reinstein, Abdolmohammadi, Tate, and Miller (2014) the U.S. Congress enacted the Sarbanes–Oxley Act (SOX, 2002) to improve corporate financial reporting, and to increase (1) manager responsibility and transparency; (2) attention to internal controls; and (3) audit quality and auditor independence. While SOX (2002) focuses on public companies, many states in the U.S. now require not-for-profit entities to adopt certain SOX provisions. We address whether governmental entities should do the same by adopting the SOX (2002) in addition to the PFM Act, 2016 as amended.

Although the Public Financial Management Act, 2016 and the Audit Service Act – 2000 (Act 584) are there to regulate the conduct and administration of public finance in Ghana it is still in the sovereign will of the people to find a more arrogated means to boost public confidence in public administrators or various government financial decisions owing to plethora of reports by previous and current years Audit reports and other public and both local and international anti-corruption agencies (Ghana Integrity Initiative and the Transparency International, World bank among others) reports on serious financial malfeasance including misappropriation and misapplication of public funds as a results the CPI (Corruption Perception Index, 2016 and 2017) index ranked Ghana among the most corrupt countries in the world.

The Sarbanes-Oxley Act provisions increase monitoring of corporate managers by mandating a majority of independent board of directors, that requires more extensive internal control over financial reporting and imposing numerous civil and criminal penalties and punitive sanctions for fraud and other violations (Gu & Zhang, 2017). The foregoing arrangements due to the enactment of the SOX Act provisions was to ensure holistic changes in corporate governance that are expected to have wide-ranging and extensive influences on corporate policies (Gu & Zhang, 2017). Comparing this Act to the PFM Act, 2016 it is clear that the SOX contains sanctions which are punitive and preventive than the PFM Act, 2016.

The auditor general of Ghana based on its 2016 audit review, whomp that *'we certified a total claim of GH¢6,331,326,592.29 out of a total of GH¢11,810,579,603.55. We have in accordance with Article 187(7)(b) of the Constitution disallowed a total claim of GH¢5,479,253,011.26 of which payment cannot be made without complying with Article 187(9) of the Constitution'* (Audit Report, 2016).

It is indefatigably perspicuous that this findings is detrimental to the economic health of every developing country. Also, whiles the Ghana Public Financial Management Act, 2016 as amended has given the necessary directives toward the convergence in public sector accounting, auditing, and financial reporting there are still significant measures to ameliorate public financial management. However, Reinstein et al. (2014) posit that subjecting public and governmental institutions to Sarbanes Oxley legislation entails high implementation and administrative costs (Krishnan, Rama, & Zhang, 2008) and that has the potency to outweigh its benefits (Engel, Hayes, & Wang, 2007; Zhang, 2007).

It is interesting to note that until date there has not been a single paper to assess and evaluate the impact of SOX (2002) as passed by the US congress to text what bearing it may have in the case Ghana and in comparison with the PFM Act, 2016 and other West African States. Even in the US today only two studies has investigated SOX (2002) - Enhancing accountability: should Sarbanes-Oxley-like legislation be expanded to the local sector Frank and Fink (2008) and Auditors' and governmental financial officers' views on expanding the Sarbanes–Oxley Act provisions to state and local governments - Reinstein et al. (2014) in which Frank and Fink (2008) who reported results about a study conducted on 132 Florida and Ohio government finance officers. Their study affirm for (a) extension of the SOX Act provisions relating to adopting principal officer certification, (b) demanding the use of an independent audit committee for larger cities and the later Reinstein et al. (2014) who did indefatigably great work and extended this study to include various other SOX (2002) provisions by assessing and measuring two groups in a Midwestern state

that are involved solely and deeply in the governmental financial reporting process, government financial officers (GFOs) and their external auditors. The findings according to Reinstein et al. (2014) were that government organization's Finance Officers are in agreement with SOX-like provisions for governmental entities, specifically in the adoption of general SOX-like Act provisions for entities accepting federal funds, and for specific provisions related to a PCAOB-like regulatory body, improved independence standards, audit partner rotation, independent audit committees, management assessment and reporting on internal controls, and increased penalties and sanctions for guileful behaviour (Reinstein et al., 2014). According to Reinstein et al. (2014) Auditors were neutral or not supportive of applying general SOX-like provisions to governmental entities. They were only in support of specific provisions relating independence standards, management assessment and reporting on internal controls, and increased penalties for fraudulent behaviour (Reinstein et al., 2014).

It is against the limited nature in respect of the scope about the two findings as postulated by Frank and Fink (2008) and Reinstein et al. (2014) that this study sought to include Lecturers and Accountants to the existing findings. We extend this study in the public sector of Ghana and the sub-regions of the West African states since they all operate similar regulations like the US. The survey extends to public institution in three major cities in Ghana as Accra, Kumasi and Takoradi which will include MDA's, MMDA's and many other public agencies. In doing this we target both internal and external auditors, the institute of Chartered Accountants Ghana, public finance officers (PFOs) and some selected lecturers of Public sector accounting in Major Universities in Ghana.

2. Literature review

Theoretical and Conceptual framework

2.1 The Sarbanes-Oxley Act (2002)

The enactment of the Sarbanes-Oxley Act as passed in 2002 as a result of widely infamous scandalous corporate governance operations in organization such as Enron, was intended to deter fraud in publicly traded corporations. Nearly for some few years ago, when it almost became a norm every day there will be a new report that a public company was in the process of re-stating its earnings, trying all legal means possible to granted a bankruptcy protection, fighting criminal indictments or if not all of the above. The Act is so comprehensive such that it extends boards' financial oversight responsibilities and imposed new financial disclosure requirements. Only two of these provisions applied to non-profits and especially in the case of Ghana. It is based on these underlying shortfalls that led to the Enactment of the PFM Act, 2016 (Act 921) in Ghana. The passage of the SOX Act provisions, nonetheless quickly spurred discussions about non-profit accountability especially in governmental organizations and whether or not non-profit institutions and corporations should adhere to certain provisions of the SOX Act, either on a voluntary or mandatory basis and that laws must be passed to extend it to non-profits.

Again, there are some key provisions in the SOX Act, more specifically Section 301 (audit committee's oversight of the issuers accounting, auditing and internal control procedures), 302 (yearly certification of the CEO and CFO's) and 404 (the assessment by management on the effectiveness of internal controls over financial reporting) have enhanced the role of management and board of directors in their oversight responsibility and reporting process within the organization (Lander, 2004).

Thus an increase in accountability and transparency within public organizations in other that the shareholders have a better understanding and insight of the business practices, processes and financial operations within such organizations. For example, Martin (2003) posits that Deloitte & Touché chief executive noted that as a result of SOX, audit committees are more involved and have deepened their understanding of the financial reporting process and accounting policies within their organizations. The executive also noted that SOX has enhanced transparency and reduced the risk of corporate fraud in many organizations. In addition, an audit committee chair noted that audit committees have doubled the time spent on audit related matters and that boards are more deeply involved in controls and are better informed of the organization's performance as a result of SOX. Records of accounting and other violations at corporate entities have seen an exponential upswing during the last few years. It was hardly alarming in the face of those reforms when the US legislature took action. President Bush signed the 2002 Corporate Accounting

Reform and Investor Protection Act, now almost generally referred to as the Sarbanes-Act of (2002) SOX or the Act, on 30 July 2002 (Pub. L. No. 107–204 116 Stat. 745). Despite its extensive drafting and implementation, SOX has had and is likely to continue to have significant consequences not only for public corporations, but for all corporations in the US (Spedding, 2009).

Spedding (2009) much farther argues that it is important to acknowledge the depth of SOX (2002) first. While the scope of the Act may seem quite constrained, at least in its face, the more accurate response may be that only time will tell the full extent of the Act. SOX only applies to public enterprises and the accounting companies which audit them on their own terms. In the long-term, however, the reforms introduced by SOX (2002) on corporate governance and accounting would become institutionalized as a set of policies and procedures, implemented as necessary by not-for-profit firms. Therefore, it is likely that nations, and indeed the United States themselves, may eventually agree to apply in the same way to private companies the principles set out in SOX 2002. This suggests that the origin of the Sarbanes-Oxley Act (SOX Act, 2002) law was that fraudulent research uncovered and highlighted significant gaps in the management of top corporations and market control environments. If government officials and legislatures have no commitment to combating corruption in public institutions, the gains of this Act would go worthless.

2.1.1 The need for SOX Act (2002) in Public Sector Financial Management

In response to fraud prevention in corporate America, the Sarbanes-Oxley Act 2002 (SOX) was enacted. Fraud in emerging companies like Tyco, Enron and WorldCom culminated in false financial statements that caused significant losses to investors when the fraudulent practices were subsequently unfolded. Currently SOX only applies to public companies; private companies, not-for-profit organizations and governmental entities are specifically exempt. SOX currently applies only to public firms; private firms, not - for-profit entities and government organizations are completely exempt. For example, the Senatorial Finance Committee released a draft paper in 2004 calling for better, non-profit governance, and numerous proposals are still under consideration. Some states have passed laws or implemented legislation applying such Sarbanes-Oxley Act requirements to non-profit entities (Ostrower & Bobowick, 2006). For example, the 2004 California Non-Profit Ethics Act allows charities with \$2 million or more in gross sales to have an audit committee. Some non-profits have implemented activities willingly provided for by the Act. Around the same time, attempts have been made to widen the Act's provisions to non-profits, despite complaints and concerns regarding the implications on smaller non-profits.

SOX regulations allow companies to strengthen their internal controls and external auditors to increase integrity and efficiency of the audit. Therefore, SOX laws applicable to the government would allow metropolitan, municipalities and district assemblies spending officers to minimize the risk of fraud. Some scholars agree that government agencies that implement SOX would strengthen their accountability and transparency, thereby protecting the interest of people in their governments and ensuring that stakeholders gain benefits from a well-run government (Elson & Dinkins, 2009). SOX regulations for example, effective audit committee and effective internal controls may well have avoided a Washington D.C., Public official embezzling up to \$50 million in real estate tax funds (Vershoor, 2008). This thus tells the usefulness of the Sox Act provision if extended to Ghana PFM

In addition, Reinstein et al. (2014) reacted to his previous review of the San Diego charges for violating conflict of interest rules, committing consumer fraud and hiding information on underfunded pensions and subverted assets as stated by (Reinstein et al., 2014), According to the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners, "A rule similar to the Sarbanes–Oxley Act requiring private sector presidents and CFOs to sign off financial statements would extend to public sector leaders, mayors and CFOs". In contrast to possibly reducing fraud, SOX-like provisions would improve the governance structures of the municipal sector, as SOX did for companies, and could minimize the risk of bankruptcy by enhancing financial reporting and financial management (Coates & John, 2007). Thus the application of SOX Act will greatly reduce financial fraud, enhancing financial reporting and management, improving governance and accountability and then minimize the risk of bankruptcy.

In the earlier work of (Reinstein, Abdolmohammadi, & Miller, 2010), they found that, discussions are close to neutral as to whether SOX-like laws for public activity should be implemented. Further analysis indicates that subjects with higher degree of familiarity with the SOX Act, (2002), those who work more than 40 hours a week, and those with higher experience in government practice (both in years of practice and in percentage of work being related to government accounting) are less likely to support SOX-like legislation for governmental entities. However most auditors have neutral view in the subject of extending the SOX to public financial management (Reinstein et al., 2010; Reinstein et al., 2014).

According to (Elson & Dinkins, 2009) '*The Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002 (SOX) was enacted in response to management fraud in Corporate America. Private companies and not-for-profit organizations recognized the effectiveness of various SOX provisions and have applied certain requirements (such as an audit committee and independent internal control assessments) as best practices. However, local governments are generally not as proactive and instead rely on existing structures and controls to ensure accountability and transparency in the management of taxpayers' resources*'.

They also argued that scandals and other unethical business practices tend to waste taxpayer money and undermine confidence in all levels of local governments (Elson & Dinkins, 2009). Clearly, there is a need for more oversight to ensure accountability and transparency in order to protect stake holders' interests. This paper suggested four areas in which SOX provisions could be implemented by governments in West Africa particularly Ghana in a cost effective manner to increase accountability and transparency to stakeholders. The areas are setting up an audit committee, certifying financial reports by the CEO / CFO, reviewing internal controls by the management and implementing a robust code of ethics policy by the local government (Elson & Dinkins, 2009).

The propensity for fraud and misconduct which is to be regulated by SOX is not limited to listed companies. The provisions of the Sarbanes Oxley Act addressed in the paper on enhancing accountability and transparency should be followed by governments of developing economies. This will protect the confidence of people in their government and guarantee that the stakeholders reap dividends in this form of as well.

2.1.2 Reasons why SOX Act (2002) is not necessary in the Public Sector Financial Management

The state and local governments or the public institutions are already subject to quite stringent checks and balances (legislative versus executive branches) not found in the private sector. These act as constraints and help to prevent (or detect) misconduct (Miller, 2007). It is for this reason the parliament of Ghana in 2016 passed the public financial management Act and therefore effective implementation of the PFM Act. 2016, will help reduce much of the canker of public service abuse. The institutionalisation of checks and balances established by the division of powers (splitting government into legislative, judiciary and executive branches) is a mechanism that offers good control (Miller, 2007). Another is that when officials are elected to the people responsible for keeping good controls, the voters have the final say, as voters can choose not to re-elect them. Answers to the Code of Ethics Section questions indicate that states have laws in place to protect informants or whistle blowers and take disciplinary measures against fraud, but the law does not clarify the fairness of the financial statements presentation.

Reinstein et al. (2010), posit that the main argument against adopting SOX regulation in the government sector is its high implementation and compliance costs. Krishnan et al. (2008) contend that on average it costs approximately \$2.2 million if not more to establish structures such as internal audit functions to deal with the burden of documenting and evaluating the internal controls in response to SOX's Section 404. Using stock price and investor trust as cost surrogates, the authors found that compliance with SOX had cost U.S. companies around \$1.4 trillion, including indirect costs and potential costs of prospective anti-business regulation even without raising market expectations substantially. Government agencies are likely to incur compliance and comparable costs of enforcement as the comparatively higher SOX costs incurred by minor public bodies (Miller, 2007), since many public entities are small in size (e.g., small cities, districts, and metropolis).

Besides explicit financial costs, implementing SOX had major opportunity costs, especially for smaller companies, such as postponing operational improvements and information technology investments.

Similarly, SOX costs will most likely eliminate existing government entities' events and programs and prevent creating new ones that support the public good. Another direct and major cost is additional human resource burdens associated with adopting SOX provisions. Large corporations often have more access to accountants, lawyers and other experts to ensure compliance; while governmental entities usually have limited access to such support and will probably need to obtain these resources at a disproportionately larger cost as compared to public companies (Gilkeson, 2006). However, the 2016 audit report suggests that internal auditors in various public institutions be made an agency under the audit service to guarantee its independence.

The rebuttal about SOX's high cost of introducing and complying is that its advantages outweigh its costs. Although the SEC was responsive to SOX critics' cost-benefit analysis, it maintains that SOX's implementation and enforcement costs have been higher than the benefits in many instances (Reinstein et al., 2014). For example, (Zhang (2007)) in-depth look at SOX's economic consequences found 70 percent of respondents to a *CFO Magazine* readers' survey believing that SOX's costs outweighed its benefits.

Another difference between the public and government sectors and, thus an argument against SOX regulation for governmental entities is that SOA was written to respond to for-profit company fraud (Reinstein et al., 2014). Since profit oriented and government organizations have different missions and activities, proponents argue that for both types of organizations, one single solution may not be sufficient. Furthermore, for-profit companies can change their status and decide to file as private companies to avoid SOX rules (Gilkeson, 2006; Reinstein et al., 2010). Again situational differences as in the case of America and Ghana or West Africa far differ and as such one enactment cannot be applicable to all situations. However, government entities cannot change their status and must accept any SOX-like legislation costs.

Finally, financial statements consumers and purposes vary between profit oriented and governmental or public bodies. Former corporations' financial statements help their users make expenditure and credit decisions in pursuit of financial performance, while government agencies' financial statements are explicitly designed to assist their users in evaluating the integrity and effectiveness of funds used to make political election and tax appropriations decisions (Reinstein et al., 2010). Consequently, a one-fits-all solution like SOX may not be as beneficial to users of government entity financial statements as to users of for-profit company financial statements.

2.2 Conceptual framework

2.2.1 Strengthening Public Financial Management (PFM) in Ghana

Onuorah and Appah (2012) proposed eleven governance concepts for improving PFM or transparency and accountability in the public sector of government in order to achieve transparency and accountability in public financial management: They are the legislative proponents of transparency; re-orientation of the value system; management transparency framework; protection of whistle blowers; establishment of an atmosphere for accountability; implementation of international standards; enhancing public sector reporting; assessing the cost of doing business; setting a benchmark for efficiency; strengthening the Public Accounts Committee; and reforming the framework of government accounting and auditing. Again Parry-michael (2010) asserts that there are four main goals that will cover effective public financial management: aggregate financial management - fiscal sustainability, resource mobilisation and allocation; operational management - performance, value for money and strategic financial planning and management; governance - transparency and accountability; fiduciary risk management - controls, compliance and oversight. Based on their suggestions and findings, we have regrouped governance principles for simplification purposes;

The Legislature must champion the course for accountability.

The legislature in Ghana and other developing countries have the constitutional responsibility to ensure that the executive are accountable to the people for the management of public funds. But the reverse is the case in Ghana, where the legislature are part and parcel of the collapse of the system. This is due to the fact that majority in Ghanaian parliament seems to support every policy of the executive whether favourable or otherwise. However, for accountability to be achieved in Ghana, the legislature must ensure

that appropriate laws and over-sight functions are properly performed by them. Again, the passage of the right to information bill must come into effect as this will compel all government officials to do what is right.

Re-orientation of Value System

Our values fundamentally affects the beliefs and mind-sets we hold. One fundamental problem in Ghana is the failure of the value system. This failure has resulted to the high level of corruption and lack of accountability by public officers. According to (Onuorah & Appah, 2012), that corrupt tendencies pervade the strata of the Nigerian society so much so that the youths, who are supposed to be the leaders of tomorrow, are neck deep in examination malpractice, 419 and internet fraud. They recommend that for Nigeria to be among the most developed economies in 2020, and then the nation's value system should be strengthened through the reintroduction of civics and ethics into the curricula of our educational system while a national orientation for the rebirth of our value system should be urgently initiated (Onuorah & Appah, 2012). Nonetheless this situation is not far from that of Ghana.

Creating environment for management accountability framework

Accountability law is only a part of the accountability process. A proper accountability framework would require that the government should put in place guidelines for preparing and approving work plan, method of monitoring plans, reporting performance, accumulation of portfolio of evidence on performance reporting, system of validation and oversight of performance reports, establishing and resourcing public accountability institutions, training public managers and guidelines for dealing with political institutions by public managers (Onuorah & Appah, 2012). An effective framework of accountability rests, besides, formal structures, on a proper environment. It requires such things as existence of a proper code of conduct, training in ethics, appearance of equal treatment by senior managers toward all employees, and unforgiving accountability of senior officers. It also means that the oversight bodies should adopt a reasonable attitude toward public managers. This was express by Onuorah and Appah (2012) as a separate framework to deal with public accountability. However these two points are intertwined and should express a common thought as the framework creates the environment for accountability

Protection of Whistle blowers

One fundamental means of achieving optimum accountability in Ghana is the protection of the whistle blowers. An effective framework of accountability requires that those who blow the whistle should be protected against any reprisal. The so-called whistle-blower provision is one of two provisions of the Act that applies to all organizations, including non-profits. Sarbanes-Oxley makes it a federal crime for any entity to retaliate against employees who report suspected fraudulent financial activities (Sarbanes, 2002). Governments should establish and intensify appropriate laws to protect the whistle-blowers.

Adoption of International Public Sector Accounting Standards

The success of accountability in the public sector in Ghana lies on the proper implementation of the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS). Public sector organizations in Ghana use the modified cash basis of accounting. It is very necessary that Ministries, Departments and Agencies should begin to use the accrual basis of accounting. A complete accrual basis of accounting would make public managers accountable for recording and safeguarding of public assets, managing public cash flows, and disclosing and discharging public liabilities (Onuorah & Appah, 2012). For government to attract foreign direct investments to it country, the financial reporting processes must be aligned with international standards (Adegite, 2010; Onuorah & Appah, 2012).

IPSAS 1 have it that public managers are in a business that affects virtually every aspect of a person's life. People, therefore, have a right to know, how the public managers are doing their business. Parliament therefore, need to take a lead in this regard and enact necessary laws making it obligatory for all public

entities to report on their performance. Public reporting on performance of departments or programs should be made mandatory. Also the government following cash-based accounting does not have a system of charging depreciation to the government assets and allocating them to various programs and projects. Thus the true cost of doing government business remains hidden. The use of IPSAS in the public sector governance will also inform managers to determine the cost of doing business.

The establishment of the benchmark of efficiency

A very important problem facing public sector managers in some West African States is the clear absence of performance benchmark (Onuorah & Appah, 2012). Public performance reporting requires that benchmarks of efficiency be devised for all ministries, departments and agencies. This should be done in consultation with the MDA's and MMDA's themselves and should remain open for periodic review and revisions.

Strengthening the Public Accounts Committee

Public accounts committees play a very significant role in accountability of public officers in Ghana. Public accounts committees should be strengthened with a system of familiarizing the members with the accounting and audit scope, approach and methods through workshops and powers to take action if their recommendations are not implemented. They should be given more authority to bite.

Change in the structure of Government Accounting and Auditing

Many West African governmental accounting systems are grossly deficient as many recommendations made in a specific year takes a long time before implementation. Financial reports are outdated and unreliable at all levels of government. Little attention is paid to financial accountability in the public service. Achua (2009) posit that there is an urgent need to protect the commonwealth from poor performance and fraud, and to protect individuals from lawless, arbitrary and capricious actions by the state's surrogate administrators (Onuorah & Appah, 2012).

Therefore, there is an urgent need to restructure the public sector accounting system taking into consideration the frailties and flaws of governmental accounting in Ghana as this recommendation is also in-line with the suggestion of the Auditor General in the 2016 Ghana supreme audit report (Ghana Audit Report, 2016). Adegite (2010) also says the rapid development and changes that have taken place in the nation's public sector since 1958. It is urgently necessary a comprehensive revision of the entire audit laws of the country with a view to aligning them with current realities and demands of globalization. The above strategies are outlined in the model below.

2.2.2 Model strategy to strengthen Public Financial Management and Good Corporate Governance

For the purpose of this study we reviewed a notable practical governance framework developed by the Independent Commission on Good Governance UK (2005) and developed a measurable framework for PFM. Although developed for public services in the UK, in our view this standard has wider applicability and provides useful guidance for countries seeking to improve their governance arrangements, particularly financial management at the Public Sector. The quality and skills of public officers particularly at the board level of government institutions as also suggested by the SOX Act (2002) is what makes an effectively governed body. This is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: The Model strategy to strengthen Public Financial Management and Good Corporate Governance

Source: Researchers’ findings

From figure 1, states or organisations must reflect on the intent and results for citizens and service users to be transparent and alert on the nature of the organization and its expected outcomes for citizens and service users to ensure that consumers provide a high-quality service and that taxpayers provide value for money. Secondly, to participate effectively in clearly defined roles and duties, to be explicit about the duties of the regulatory body, to be consistent about the obligations of non-executives and the executive by ensuring that those obligations are carried out and to be transparent about interactions between authorities and the citizens. Thirdly, fostering principles for the nation and organizations as a whole and exhibiting good governance principles by action, putting organizational values into practice, and insisting on actions by individual leaders, administrators, or chief executives that represent and demonstrate successful governance. Forth is concerned with making educated, straightforward decisions and managing risk being robust and irrefutable on how decisions are made, using knowledge, guidance and support of good quality, and ensuring that an appropriate risk management program is in place.

Fifthly, improving the governing body's capabilities, resources and expertise to be successful and certain and to ensure that appointed and elected board members, chief executives and other relevant stakeholders have the expertise, knowledge and experience they need to perform well, improving the ability of people with governance responsibilities and assessing their performance, as individuals and as a collective, and striking a balance between continuity and renewal in the membership of the governing authority. Finally, involving stakeholders and making transparency practical, recognizing formal and informal transparency relationships, taking an active and planned approach to public dialog and accountability, taking an active and planned approach to staff accountability and interacting with institutional stakeholders effectively (Independent Commission on Good Governance UK, 2005).

We do not support a one-size-fits-all framework or solution, as many countries and public sector entities may have different governance systems, but we believe that the norm will enable those involved in public service governance not only to recognize and implement common concepts of good governance, But also identifying the benefits and shortcomings of existing processes in governance and how to develop them.

2.3 Implication of extending the SOX Act, 2002 to Public Financial Management

According to Ostrower and Bobowick (2006) the potential effect of applying the Sarbanes-Oxley legislation to non-profit organizations would result in making some of the legislation of the Sarbanes-Oxley Act mandatory, forcing large numbers of non-profits to modify their activities, but passing others will result in little improvement. Their preliminary results indicate the solution is nuanced, and it's not the same for all

regulations or varying size government institutions. For example, because making loans to its directors was uncommon for most MDA's and MMDA's, additional legislation banning government agencies from providing such loans would have an effect on relatively few organisations. Conversely, a law or best practice directive calling for government agencies to set up a separate and independent audit committee will have a pervasive effect, as most of them actually do not have such a committee (Ostrower & Bobowick, 2006).

The effect will vary according to scale, too. That is a larger proportion of independent not-for-profit will have to reform in order to comply, so it would be very difficult for more local government agencies to comply. Their results strongly reinforce the usefulness of considering the wildly different effect, expense, and benefit of applying legislation to differing sizes of government entities, as some laws and regulations already exist, by excluding institutions below a certain scale. If lawmakers will enact future legislation to expand Sarbanes-Oxley to non-profits, the passage of the Act has already had a significant impact on discussion and debate regarding non-profit governance practice. This involves testing the case of West Africa, especially Ghana, as we are setting out to find better ways or means of ensuring sustainable development through public financial management.

3. Methodology

The research strategy adopted for this study is intuitive and logically driven as it uses quantitative research approach that allows for the establishment of causal relationships between variables and provides important insights into the interrelationships that could exist between very many variables of interest and enhances our understating of their links. The method also involves strict definition of terms and measurement of variables (i.e. operationalisation of the variables) of interest, so that the researcher is actually measuring what he sets out to measure and not another phenomenon (Adelopo, 2010).

3.1 Development of survey instrument

We read and examined major SOX provisions, read many literature pertaining to this study and thoroughly examined the Public Financial Management Act, 2016 including the Audit Service Act 2000 (Act 584) also adopted most strategies used by (Reinstein et al., 2010; Reinstein et al., 2014) to develop our survey instrument. Our instrument was pretested with highly experienced senior public finance officers and six accounting professors who have several years of experience in the teaching of public sector accounting. This was done to test the validity and reliability of our survey instrument and in effect improve the work of early researchers.

3.2 Participants

In extending the study of early researchers, we surveyed public finance officers and accountants who are members of the institute of chartered accountants Ghana (ICAG), lecturers and both internal and external auditors. The public finance officers (PFO's) were made up finance officers at post at various governmental institutions who were willing to contribute to the study, same were the public accountants who are qualified and certified by the ICAG. The lecturer were made up of professors and senior lecturers who have thought the subject of public sector accounting or governmental accounting for several years. Again views of internal auditors of various institutions were sought for due to Auditor General of Ghana assertion that they should be made to work under them. The sampled external auditors consisted of members of several local and national public accounting firms that audit governmental entities.

In all two hundred and two (202) PFO's, accountants, lecturers, internal and external auditors as defined in the criteria above participated in the study as recognition was given to only those who completed their questionnaire entirely. The final schedule of the participants is slated in Table 1.

Table 1: schedule of participants

Participants	Frequency	Percentage (%)
PFO's	94	46.5
Accountants	40	19.8
Lecturers	25	12.4
Internal auditors	25	12.4
External Auditors	18	08.9
	202	100.0

4.0 Results

4.1 Analysis of demographic characteristics of study participants

Table I: Descriptive statistics on demographic variables

Subjects	Mean, \pm SD				χ^2 (Sig.)
	PFOs n=94 (46.5%)	Acc/Lecs n=65 (32.2%)	Auditors n=43 (21.3%)	Total N= 202 (100.0%)	
Gender					
Male	43 (45.7%)	43 (66.2%)	27 (62.8%)	113 (55.9%)	7.53 (.023)
Female	51 (54.3%)	22 (33.8%)	16 (37.2%)	89 (44.1%)	
Working Experience					
< 5 yrs.	37 (39.4%)	15 (23.1%)	9 (20.9%)	61 (30.2%)	7.22 (.125)
5 – 10 yrs.	47 (50.0%)	40 (61.5%)	27 (62.8%)	114 (56.4%)	
> 10 yrs.	10 (10.6%)	10 (15.4%)	7 (16.3%)	27 (13.4%)	
Qualification					
HND	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.1%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (1.0%)	13.17 (.040)
Degree	48 (51.1%)	19 (29.2%)	16 (37.2%)	83 (41.1%)	
Masters	44 (46.8%)	42 (64.6%)	24 (55.8%)	110 (54.5%)	
PhD/Professor	2 (2.1%)	2 (3.1%)	3 (7.0%)	7 (3.5%)	

PFO=Public Finance Officers, Acc/Lecs=Accountants and Lecturers, Auditors (Internal and External)

From the expected 230 study participants, a total of 202 eventually participated in the study because partially completed as well as soiled questionnaires were removed from the pack. As shown in Table I, from the 202 total participants 94 (46.5%) were Public Finance Officers, 65 (32.2%) were accountant and lecturers both in private and governmental organizations, and 43 (21.3%) were both internal and external Auditors. Approximately, 56% were males, 56% have had between 5 – 10 years of working experiences with their respective organisations, 55% were master's degree holders as at the time of the study.

Table II summarises responses regarding the general perceptions about SOX 2002. Overview of the results gives the impression that all groups were aware of what the SOX 2002 is about. With a mean statistic (PFOs=3.54, Acc/Lecs=3.38, Auditors=3.21). Overall, scores showed that the respondents were aware of the accounting provisions of SOX (mean=3.41, \pm SD=.710). Their level of awareness regarding the SOX as well as the Accounting provisions in the SOX were both statistically significant at .033 and .023 respectively.

Table II: Descriptive Statistics: General Perception about SOX Act Provision (2002)

Subjects	Mean, \pm SD				χ^2 (Sig.)
	PFOs n=94	Acc/Le cs n=65	Auditors n=43	Total N= 202	
Awareness of the SOX	3.54 (.501)*	3.38 (.784)*	3.21 (.914)	3.42 (.710)	3.46 (.033)
Awareness of the accounting provisions of SOX	3.54 (.501)*	3.37 (.802)	3.19 (.932)*	3.41 (.722)	3.859 (.023)
The SOX provisions enhance accounting profession reputation	4.06 (.759)	3.95 (.926)	4.84 (.374)*	4.19 (.827)	20.13 (.001)
SOX should be extended to public sector financial management	4.01 (.769)	3.49 (.831)	3.02 (.266)*	3.63 (.813)	29.87 (.001)
SOX increase auditor's independence	4.16 (.738)	4.00 (.848)	4.79 (.514)*	4.24 (.789)	16.06 (.001)
Auditors of public sector organisations should be held to the same independence as private organizations	4.20 (.837)	4.25 (.730)	4.86 (.351)	4.36 (.767)	13.300 (.001)
Internal auditors of public sector organisations should be made to work under the audit service of Ghana as suggested by the auditor general as a way to guarantee their independence (NB: not in SOX)	2.68 (.975)*	2.55 (.867)	1.95 (.486)	2.49 (.899)	10.916 (.001)
The general public has confidence in the audited financial statement	3.72 (.754)*	3.82 (.864)	4.67 (.606)*	3.96 (.848)	24.494 (.001)
All stakeholders of government institutions who have an interest in their financial statements do not care about government institutions following different standards than auditors of public institutions	3.01 (.711)*	3.89 (.850)*	3.00 (.378)	3.29 (.816)	34.624 (.001)

PFO=Public Finance Officers, Acc/Lecs=Accountants and Lecturers, Auditors

The results showed a sense of strong agreement among the respondents regarding the assertion that the SOX provisions will enhance the accounting profession reputation (mean = 4.19, \pm SD=.827). PFOs were more in

favour of extending the SOX Act provision to Public sector financial management compared to the Accountants and Lecturers and Auditors (mean=4.01, 3.49, 3.02) respectively. The results showed that the differences among the groups were statistically significant. Additionally, the assertion that SOX increases auditor's independence was firmly accepted by the respondents (mean=4.24); however, the Auditors (mean = 4.79) were much more in favour compared to the PFOs (mean = 4.16) and the Accountants and Lecturers (mean = 4.00). The weakest results among the variables had to do with making internal auditors of public sector organisation to work under the Ghana audit service as suggested by the auditor general as a way of guaranteeing their independence. Overall mean was 2.49 and contrary to expectations Auditors were the least in favour of such a provision with mean statistic of (mean = 1.95, \pm SD = .899) compared to the PFOs and Accountants and Lecturers (mean=2.68 and mean=2.55) respectively. Chi-square statistic on the variable showed a statistically significant differences were observed in the ratings of the respondents ($\chi^2=10.916$, $p=.001$).

Table III Specific Perceptions about SOX 2002

Subjects	Mean, \pm SD				χ^2 (Sig.)
	PFOs n=94	Acc/Lecs n=65	Auditors n=43	Total N= 202	
SOX requires a Public Accounting Oversight Board of five full-time members (2 – CPA and three non-CPA). A similar regulation should be set in the case of public sector accounting.	3.98 (.655)*	3.74 (.871)	3.23 (.480)	3.64 (.830)	6.924 (.001)
The public sector accounting should be set to have an independent audit committee just like the private sector	2.24 (1.114)	3.25* (1.287)	3.12 (.324)	2.75 (1.162)	20.165 (.001)
Non-audit service should not be pre-approved by the audit committee	3.22 (.869)	3.51 (1.264)	4.00 (.577)*	3.48 (1.008)	9.529 (.001)

PFO=Public Finance Officers, Acc/Lecs= Accountants and Lecturers, Auditors

Table III summarises the responses on the specific perfections about SOX 2002. The respondents somewhat agreed (mean=3.64, \pm SD=.830) that a Public Accounting Oversight Board of five full-time members should be instituted for the Public Sector Accounting sector. Statistically, PFO's had the strongest of conviction (mean = 3.98) on the subject than the Accountants and Lecturers and the Auditors. The majority of the participants (mean=2.75, \pm SD=1.162) agreed with the assertion that public sector accounting should be given an independent audit committee, just like the private sector and this findings supports the work of Reinstein et al. (2014).

Amongst the various groups, the Accountants and Lecturers had the strongest of claims against the other groups. Differences observed in the responses were, however, statistically significant ($\chi^2=20.165$, $p<.05$). The majority of the respondents agreed (mean=3.48, \pm SD=1.008) that non-audit service should not be pre-approved by the audit committee. The trend of the responses implies that apart from the introduction of an independent audit committee into the public sector; the participants mainly supports the provision that public accounting oversight board. Also, they recommend that the non-audit service should not pre-approved by the audit committee.

Table IV: Audit Independence

Subjects	Mean, \pm SD				χ^2 (Sig.)
	PFOs n=94	Acc/Lecs n=65	Auditors n=43	Total N= 202	
The public financial management Act 2016 and the audit service Act 2000 (Act 584) provide adequate and detailed independence provisions. Thus, there is no need for additional regulation such SOX	3.76 (.876)	3.74 (.871)	3.23 (.480)*	3.64 (.830)	6.924 (.001)
The SOX Act prohibits public accounting firms from performing non-audit service. The PFM Act 2016 remains silent as to whether or not these non-audit services must be performed, what is the extent of your agreement to the fact that these provisions in SOX.	2.24 (1.114)	3.25 (1.287)	3.12 (.324)*	2.75 (1.162)	20.165 (.001)
Internal audit units of public institutions should be a function under the Audit Service to enhance their independence	3.22 (.869)	3.51 (1.264)*	4.00 (.577)*	3.48 (1.008)	9.529 (.001)
Finance directors, chief accounting officers should not be employed by government institutions if they have worked for government entities audit firms for less than one year.	4.27 (.706)	4.09 (.655)*	3.74 (.658)*	4.10 (.705)	8.693 (.001)
Audits of governmental entities should include second review partner	4.30 (.653)*	4.25 (.708)*	4.21 (.412)	4.26 (.627)	.324 (.724)
The audit and second review partners on government entity audit should rotate off every five years	4.29 (.616)	4.49 (.687)	4.84 (.374)*	4.47 (.632)	12.509 (.001)

PFO=Public Finance Officers, Acc/Lecs= Accountants and Lecturers, Auditors

Table IV presents the results on the independence of Audit as part of the provisions in the SOX 2002. The respondents agreed that there is no need for additional regulations such as SOX 2002 because the public finance management Act 2016 and the audit service Act 2000 (Act 584) provide adequate and detailed independence provisions. PFOs (mean=3.76) were in favour of the assertion that the Accountants and Lecturers (mean=3.74) and Auditors (mean=3.23). The differences between the auditors and the PFOs and Accountants and Lecturers were statistically significant. The findings are not much surprising since auditors, in particular, do not want further restrictions and control over their activities.

Accountants and Lecturers and Auditors agreed compared with the PFOs who disagreed with the assertion that the SOX Act prohibits public accounting firms from performing non-audit service given the PFM Act 2016 is silent on the provision (mean=3.25, mean=3.12 and mean=2.24). The observed differences in rating between Audit and PFOs and Accountants and Lecturers were statistically significant. Generally, the respondents were not in favour that the SOX would prevent public accounting firms from performing non-audit service in effect, giving backing to the adoption of the SOX into the Ghanaian public financial sector.

Audit and second review partners on government entity audit should rotate off every five years obtained the strongest results among the respondents. All scores were significantly stronger than neutral (mean= 3.0) for all the three groups (PFO mean=4.29, Accountants and Lecturers mean=4.49 and Audit mean=4.47).

Table V: Records Retention and Whistle Blowers

Subjects	Mean, ±SD				χ ² (Sig.)
	PFOs n=94	Acc/Le cs n=65	Auditors n=43	Total N= 202	
Employees in public sector organizations who commit fraud and destroy records or fail to report fraud should face punitive penalties	4.47 (.651)	4.54 (.686)	4.81 (.394)	4.56 (.630)	4.701 (.010)
Government entities should not face severe criminal penalties if any of its employees alter, destroy, mutilate, conceal or make false entry in a document or record	1.46 (.501)	1.43 (.499)	1.65 (.529)	1.49 (.511)	11.893 (.001)
Public accountants or audit firms should face severe penalties for deliberately not keeping all audit or review papers for at least five years	1.62 (.705)	1.62 (.842)	1.91 (.811)	1.68 (.779)	2.386 (.095)
Government employees who report fraudulent acts should be guarded against unlawful dismissal and unwarranted discipline	4.45 (.666)	4.77 (.425)	4.63 (.489)	4.59 (.577)	6.458 (.002)
There should be an established and well-defined procedure for receiving and handling complaints relating to accounting and auditing issues	4.36 (.483)	4.82 (.391)	4.88 (.324)	4.62 (.487)	32.542 (.001)
There should be a procedure established to protect whistle-blowers	4.34 (.476)	4.80 (.403)	4.93 (.258)	4.61 (.488)	39.409 (.001)

PFO=Public Finance Officers, Acc/Lecs=Private Finance Officers, Auditors

Relative to records retention and whistle-blowers, the Auditors posted the strongest of agreement (mean=4.81) compared to the PFOs (mean=4.47) and Accountants and Lecturers (mean=4.54) concerning punishment for public sector employees who commit fraud and destroy records or fail to report fraud. The difference in the responses was statistically significant (χ²=4.701, p<.05). Accountants and Lecturers strongly disagreed (mean=1.43) compared to the PFOs (mean=1.46) and (mean=1.65) that government entities should not face severe criminal penalties if any of its employees alter, destroy, mutilate, conceal or make a false entry in a document or record. The observed differences in responses were statistically significant (χ²=11.893, p<.001).

Again, there was strong agreement (overall mean=4.62, ±SD=.487) that there should be an establishment as well as a well-defined procedure for receiving and handling complaints relating to accounting and auditing issues. Auditors had the strongest expressions of agreement (mean=4.88) as against, PFOs (mean=4.36) and Accountants and Lecturers (mean=4.82). Observed differences in scores among the respondents were statistically significant (χ²=32.542, p=.001) suggesting that the participants are in favour of establishing a well-defined procedure for receiving and handling complaints relating to accounting and auditing issues.

That said, again, the Auditors as expected had the strongest of conviction (mean=4.93) compared to the other groups (PFOs mean= 4.34 and Accountants and Lecturers mean= 4.80) that a procedure should be established to protect whistle-blowers.

Table VI: Reporting and Disclosures

Subjects	PFOs n=94	Acc/Lecs n=65	Mean, \pm SD		χ^2 (Sig.)
			Auditors n=43	Total N= 202	
Management should assess and make representations about the effectiveness of the internal control structure and financial reporting procedure	4.31 (.640)	4.28 (.625)	4.40 (.541)	4.32 (.614)	.495 (.610)
Auditors should review, test, and report on management representations of internal control structures as part of their routine audit structure	4.36 (.653)	4.72 (.451)	4.88 (.324)	4.59 (.577)	16.996 (.001)*
Auditors should review, test, and report on their independent assessment of internal control structures	4.36 (.653)	4.46 (.502)	4.53 (.505)	4.43 (.580)	1.459 (.235)
It should be the ultimate responsibility of Finance Officers or director of finance, Chief accountants, and other senior officers of government entity to clarify that the financial statement is free from material misstatements and that proper internal control system is in place	4.55 (.561)	4.63 (.486)	4.60 (.495)	4.59 (.523)	.455 (.641)
Government entities should be required to disclose in their periodic reports the number of fees paid to auditors for audit and non-audit services	4.39 (.553)	4.69 (.465)	4.67 (.474)	4.55 (.528)	8.235 (.001)*

PFO=Public Finance Officers, Acc/Lecs=Private Finance Officers, Auditors

Table VI presents the analysis on reporting and disclosures as part of the SOX 2002 provisions. The items sought to assess their suitability when applied to the Ghanaian context. The results show that the Auditors were much in favour of management, making representations about the effectiveness of the internal control structure and financial reporting procedure (m=4.40, m= 4.28, m=4.31).

The overall result supports the position of the various groups (mean=4.32, \pm SD=.614). Again, the respondents agreed that Auditors should review, test and report on management representation of internal control structures as part of their routine audit structure (mean=4.59, \pm SD=.577); yet again Auditors were much in support of this provision being introduced into the Ghanaian financial sector. Auditors obtained a mean statistic of (mean=4.88) compared to the PFOs (m=4.36) and Accountants and Lecturers (mean=4.72). The observed differences in the responses were found to be statistically significant.

Furthermore, the respondents agreed strongly (mean=4.59, \pm SD=.580) that there should be the ultimate responsibility of Finance Officers or director of finance, Chief accountants and other senior officers of government entities to ensure that proper internal control systems are in place. Accountants and Lecturers (mean=4.63) were more in agreement with the assertion compared to the PFOs (mean=4.60) and Auditors (mean=4.55). There was statistically strong agreement (mean=4.55, \pm SD=.528) among the participants that government entities should be required to disclose in their periodic reports the number of fees paid to auditors for audit and non-audit services. The differences in the scores attained by the groups were statistically significant ($\chi=8.235$, p=.001).

Conclusion

Overall, the study findings are hinged on three elements; the Independence of Auditor, Records Retention and Whistle-blowers as well as reporting and disclosures. The results suggest that participants are in favour of the introduction of SOX 2002 provisions on record retention and whistle-blowers into the Ghanaian Financial sector to deal with financial records management and to check against fraud. Whereas there was strong support for the introduction of SOX 2002 provisions regarding financial reporting and disclosures should be introduced into the Ghanaian financial sector. The results show that the respondents remain in favour of making provisions that protect the independence of the Audit function as a critical component of Public Financial Management. It is interesting to note that stakeholders in the Ghanaian financial sector to a greater extent are in favour of the introduction of the SOX Act provision (2002) into the Ghanaian public

financial management. We also found strong support for auditor independences rules similar to the SOX Act provisions. Whiles majority of lecturers believe that extending the SOX Act provision to Ghana's PFM is not a means to an end as they believe the PFM ACT (2016) Act 921 have enough provisions to deal with most systemic challenges in the local government sector in Ghana. Conversely, among the stakeholders, Auditors were most influential in their support for the introduction of the SOX Act provisions into the Ghanaian public financial sector. And asserted a strong support for management assessment of and reporting on internal controls, and punitive penalties meted out for destruction of records, fraud and failure to report fraud. We also suggest that government should give much support to the right to information bill to actualise it intended purpose.

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